

STUDIES IN INDIGOID DYES. PART V. (METHYL)THONAPHTHENE-PHENANTHRENE-INDIGOS

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Phenanthraquinone and its 2-nitro derivative have been condensed with 4-, 5-, 6-, and 7-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene respectively. The isomeric (methyl)thionaphthene-phenanthrene-indigos are chocolate and violet dyestuffs. The changes in colour due to the substitution of a methyl group in 4, 5, 6, and 7 positions of the thionaphthene nucleus of some of these dyestuffs were found out by location of their absorption maxima in the microphotograms. It is revealed that they are of the same order as those of the isomeric indole-(methyl) thionaphthene-indigos, (methyl) thionaphthene-acanthrylene-indigos, dimethylthioindigos and *bis*-(methyl)thionaphthene-ethylene-indigos previously studied by the author.

It has been established recently by the author that in the case of asymmetrical thioindigoid vat dyes, the isomeric indole-(methyl)thionaphthene-indigos, and methyl (thionaphthene)-acanthrylene-indigos, and also in the case of symmetrical dyes, the isomeric dimethylthioindigos and the *bis*(methyl)thionaphthene-ethylene-indigos, the change in their colours may be arranged in the order : 5-methyl dye > 4-methyl dye > 6-methyl dye > 7-methyl dye, and the position of colour of the parent dye of each of the series mentioned above is next to that of its 5-methyl substituted dye (Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 21, 87, 391).

As a further test of this general observation, the author has studied in the present paper the influence of a methyl group when it is present in all the theoretically possible different positions of the thionaphthene ring of the 2-thionaphthene-9'-phenanthrene-indigo and its 2'-nitro derivative only (Friedländer, Herzog and Voss, *Ber.*, 1922, 55, 1591 ; Pummerer and Luther, *ibid.*, 1931, 64, 831 ; Dutt, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 99), which are also good instances of asymmetrical dyes belonging to phenanthraquinone series.

With this object in view, 4-, 5-, 6-, and 7-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthenes (E.P., 279489/27 ; Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 15, 23 ; Auwers and Arndt, *Ber.*, 1909, 42, 541 ; Friedländer, *Ber.*, 1876, 9, 589 ; Auwers and Thies, *Ber.*, 1920, 53, 2293 ; Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* 1943, 20, 37) were condensed with phenanthraquinone, and its 2-nitro derivative only. The vat dyes prepared now are : 2-(4-methyl)-, 2-(6-methyl)-, and 2-(7-methyl)-thionaphthene-9'-phenanthrene-indigo ; 2-(4-methyl)-, 2-(5-methyl)-, 2-(6-methyl)-, and 2-(7-methyl)-thionaphthene-9'-(2'-nitro)-phenanthrene-indigo. The 2-(5-methyl)thionaphthene-9'-phenanthrene-indigo was described before by Guha and Basu-Mallick (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 395).

These dyes are chocolate and violet coloured substances, generally soluble in high boiling solvents, such as pyridine, xylene, nitrobenzene and aniline. They dissolve in concentrated sulphuric acid producing a characteristic colouration. They generally melt at a high temperature, above which, when strongly heated, they volatilise. Their dyeing shades on wool from an acid bath are uniformly and fully developed.

But the shades on cloth from the hydrosulphite vat, in which the dyes dissolve with a yellow colour, are light and at the same time unsatisfactory, although the dyes themselves are deep (*cf.* the isomeric naphthathiophene-9'-phenanthrene-indigos, Dutt, *Ber.*, 1934, 67, 5, 1319).

On comparing the colours of these isomeric (methyl)thionaphthene-phenanthrene-indigos and their dyeing shades, it is found that their change in colour is also of the same order as those of the asymmetrical dyes of isatin and aceanthrenequinone series, and the symmetrical vat-dyes of thioindigo and *bisthionaphthene-ethylene-indigo* series (*loc. cit.*). For the quantitative measurement of the absorption maxima of these dyes and to substantiate the qualitative views, the absorption spectra of some of the dyes have been measured in nitrobenzene solution. For this purpose, the isomeric (methyl)thionaphthene-(nitro)-phenanthrene-indigos are chosen, as it is found easy to make a sharp distinction between their colours. The absorption curves (Figs. 1 & 2) drawn by a microphotometer and also the absorption maxima (Table I) found out by calculation from a graph readily confirm what is deduced by the qualitative examination.

TABLE I

Me=Methyl ; T=Thionaphthene ; P=Phenanthrene-indigo.	
Compounds.	Absorption maxima
2-(4-Me)-T-9'(2'-nitro)-P	5515 A.U.
2-(5-Me)-T-9'(2'-nitro)-P	5585
2-(6-Me)-T-9'(2'-nitro)-P	5495
2-(7-Me)-T-9'(2'-nitro)-P	5475

It did not seem worth while to attempt to prepare more of (methyl)thionaphthene-phenanthrene-indigos having different types of substituents in the phenanthrene part of the dye molecule, as it is observed that the dyes of this class generally impart to cloth lighter shades of their real colour which stand greatly in their way of fulfilling the chief object of utilising them as vat colours [the isomeric indole-(methyl)thionaphthene-indigos and (methyl)-thionaphthene-acenaphthylene-indigos whose beautiful shades have been rapidly developed on cotton as well as on wool, Guha, *loc. cit.*; Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 20, 37; 1944, 21, 91).

EXPERIMENTAL.

2-(4-Methyl)-thionaphthene-9'-phenanthrene-indigo separated as a dark chocolate (almost black) crystalline precipitate when phenanthraquinone (1.04 g.) and 4-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.82 g.) in 47 c.c. of glacial acetic acid and 2 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid were boiled for 15-20 minutes in an atmos-

FIG. 1.

Curves P and Q refer respectively to 2-(4-methyl)- and 2-(5-methyl)-thionaphthene-9'-(2'-nitro)-phenanthrene-indigo.

FIG. 2.

R S R S R S R S R

Curves R and S refer respectively to 2-(6-methyl) and 2-(7-methyl) thionaphthene-9'-(2'-nitro)-phenanthrene-indigo.

phere of carbon dioxide. The dye (0.584 g.) was purified by dissolving in a mixture of pyridine and nitrobenzene and precipitated by water, washed with dilute alcohol and hot water. It melts above 295°. It is moderately soluble in alcohol, acetic acid and benzene. It dissolves in cold concentrated sulphuric acid to a faint greenish brown colour. It dyes wool and cloth in blackish brown shade. (Found : S, 9.39. $C_{23}H_{14}O_2S$ requires S, 9.04 per cent).

2(6-Methyl)thionaphthene-9'-phenanthrene-indigo was similarly obtained from phenanthraquinone (0.624 g.) and 6-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.492g.) in 45 c.c. of glacial acetic acid and 4 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid. The dark chocolate crystalline substance (0.396 g.) was purified at first by boiling with alcohol in which it is sparingly soluble and then precipitating from pyridine solution by the addition of water. It melts above 310°. It is moderately soluble in chloroform, acetic acid and benzene; sparingly soluble in acetone. The solution of the substance in cold concentrated sulphuric acid is black-brown. It dyes both wool and cloth in the same shade as the preceding compound. (Found : S, 9.45. $C_{23}H_{14}O_2S$ requires S, 9.04 per cent).

2-(7-Methyl)thionaphthene-9'-phenanthrene-indigo.—Phenanthraquinone (0.416 g.) and 7-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.328 g.) were dissolved in 25 c.c. of boiling glacial acetic acid and concentrated hydrochloric acid (3 c.c.) added when at once a lump of the dye separated; more of glacial acetic acid (20 c.c.) was added and boiled for 20 minutes. The crystalline light chocolate precipitate (0.33 g.) was purified similarly as the preceding compound melting above 300°. It is soluble in chloroform, sparingly soluble in glacial acetic acid and benzene. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid in cold producing a reddish brown colour. It imparts light brown shade to wool and blackish brown shade to cloth. (Found : S, 9.41. $C_{23}H_{14}O_2S$ requires S, 9.04 per cent).

2-(4-Methyl)thionaphthene-9'-(2'-nitro)-phenanthrene-indigo separated as a violet crystalline precipitate on treating a boiling solution of 2-nitrophenanthraquinone (0.759 g.) and 4-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.492 g.) in glacial acetic acid (95 c.c.) with concentrated hydrochloric acid (5c.c.) and heating for 15-20 minutes. The dye (0.224 g.) was obtained from xylene in star-shaped crystals melting at 302° (decomp.). It is soluble in benzene, sparingly soluble in alcohol. Cold concentrated sulphuric acid dissolves it producing a deep green solution. It dyes wool in dark violet shade from an acid bath and cotton in faint violet shade from the hydrosulphite vat. (Found : N, 3.74. $C_{23}H_{13}O_4NS$ requires N, 3.51 per cent).

2-(5-Methyl)thionaphthene-9'-(2'-nitro)-phenanthrene-indigo was similarly prepared as the 4-methyl dye from 2-nitrophenanthraquinone (1.012 g.) and 5-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.656 g.) in 122 c.c. of boiling glacial acetic acid and concentrated hydrochloric acid (5 c.c.). The violet small needle-shaped precipitate (0.898 g.) was crystallised from xylene in beautiful foliated needles melting at 280° (decomp.). It is slightly soluble in acetic acid and chloroform. The colour of the solution of the substance in cold concentrated sulphuric acid is leaf-green. It dyes both wool and cotton in the same shade as the preceding compound. (Found : N, 3.84. $C_{23}H_{13}O_4NS$ requires N, 3.51 per cent).

2-(6-Methyl)thionaphthene-9'-(2'-nitro)-phenanthrene-indigo was obtained as before from 2-nitrophenanthraquinone (1.012 g.) and 6-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.656 g.) in 120 c.c. of boiling glacial acetic acid and 6-7 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid in violet coloured crystalline precipitate (1.118g.). It was crystallised from nitrobenzene in fine small needles melting above 300° (with previous shrinking at 295°). It is moderately soluble in amyl alcohol and acetic acid, sparingly soluble in alcohol. Cold concentrated sulphuric acid dissolves it producing the same colour as the 5-methyl dye. It dyes wool violet from an acid bath and cloth in light violet shade from the hydrosulphite vat. (Found : N, 3.55. $C_{23}H_{13}O_4NS$ requires N, 3.51 per cent).

2-(7-Methyl)thionaphthene-9'-(2'-nitro)-phenanthrene-indigo.—2-Nitrophenanthraquinone (0.759 g.) was dissolved in a little more than the required quantity of boiling glacial acetic acid and to this solution 7-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.492g) was added and the solution shaken well. The resulting red-brown solution on treatment with concentrated hydrochloric acid (3-4 c.c.) and boiling in an atmosphere of carbon dioxide for about 20 minutes, gave a crystalline violet coloured substance (1 g.). It was crystallised from a mixture of nitrobenzene and xylene in dark violet dye (almost black) melting above 300°. It is sparingly soluble in acetic acid, benzene; insoluble in alcohol. Concentrated sulphuric acid dissolves it with a light yellowish green colour. It dyes wool in light violet-brown shade and cloth in blackish brown colour. (Found : N, 3.41. $C_{23}H_{13}O_4NS$ requires N, 3.51 per cent).

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